

Smart Alert for College

Mr. A. Vaishnav¹, Ms. R. Selvapriya² Msc., Mphil.

¹BSc Information Technology, ²Assistant Professor, Department of ICT,
^{1,2}Sri Krishna Adithya College of Arts and Science, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India

How to cite this paper: Mr. A. Vaishnav | Ms. R. Selvapriya Msc., Mphil. "Smart Alert for College" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-3 | Issue-3, April 2019, pp.521-522, URL: <http://www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd21716.pdf>

IJTSRD21716

Copyright © 2019 by author(s) and International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development Journal. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0) (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>)

ABSTRACT

In recent years VB.net has brought many drastic changes in building powerful web application development. This application provides a generalized solution to monitor the various works that are carried out by the Placement Cell. "Smart Alert for College" provides a simple interface for the maintenance of student placement information and to filter student interview process list based on company eligibility criteria. It can be used by educational institutes or colleges to maintain the records of students. The creation and management of accurate, up-to-date information regarding a students' academic career is critically important in the university as well as colleges. The purposed system helps the placement cell to manage the mark details of the students and their placement information and it automatically sends Interview alert to student mobile number based on company basic criteria. Smart Alert for College deals with all kind of student details, academic related reports, college details, course details, placement details. It allows to update the various placement notifications to the staff and students updated by the placement administration. It also facilitate us explore all the activities happening in the placement cell.

KEYWORDS: Placement details, maintain records, SMS, Smart Alert for College

1. INTRODUCTION

The design and implementation of a comprehensive student placement information system and user interface is to replace the current paper records. College Staff are able to directly access all aspects of a student's academic progress through a secure, online interface embedded in the college's website.

The system utilizes user authentication, displaying only information necessary for an individual's duty. Additionally, each sub-system has authentication allowing admin to create or update information in that subsystem. All data is stored securely on SQL servers managed by the college administrator and ensures highest possible level of security. The system features a complex logging system to track all users' access and ensure conformity to data access guidelines and is expected to increase the efficiency of the college's record management thereby decreasing the work hours needed to access and deliver student records to users.

Previously, the college relied heavily on paper records for this initiative. While paper records are a traditional way of managing student data and different work, there are several drawbacks to this method. First, to convey information to the students it should be displayed on the notice board and the student has to visit the notice board to check that information. It takes a very long time to convey the information to the student. Paper records are difficult to manage and track. The physical exertion required to retrieve, alter, and re-file the paper records are all non-value

added activities. This system provides a simple interface for the maintenance of student information. It can be used by educational institutes or colleges to maintain the records of students easily. Achieving this objective is difficult using a manual system as the information is scattered, can be redundant and collecting relevant information may be very time consuming. All these problems are solved using Smart Alert for College. The paper focuses on presenting information in an easy and intelligible manner which provides facilities such as updating student information, sending alerts, thus reducing paper work and automating the record generation process in an educational institute.

2. System Study

It involves studying a procedure or business in order to identify its goals and purposes and create systems and procedures that will achieve them in an efficient way. Use cases are a widely used systems analysis modeling tool for identifying and expressing the functional requirements of a system.

2.1 EXISTING SYSTEM

The existing system is manual filtration, doesn't have the flexibility to maintain and send the interview process to students. There are many possibilities for the mistake to take place when the entries or calculations are made manually. The existing system is tedious and time consuming. It also requires handling knowledge and skilled manpower. If you want to update some details it is very difficult in existing

system. Storing and retrieving process it is very difficult. Redundant data also occurred so existing system needs more memory size. The existing system is a manual system, where the admin need to compose every message individually.

2.1.1 DISADVANTAGES

- Manual work
- Storing and retrieving not easy
- No automatic messaging option available
- There is no filter process

2.2 PROPOSED SYSTEM

The drawbacks, which are faced during existing system, can be eradicated by using the proposed system. The main objective of the proposed system is to provide a user-friendly interface to college placement cell to filter student interview process list based on company eligibility criteria with efficient and easiest manner. This proposed application all filtration done without much time consuming. This windows application is a effective way to communicate with the students about their interview It will allow find to quickly find the student for interview process based on company mark criteria and send the interview alert through Send mail Service. All student details will be stored in the system so the filtration are done by the system automatically. This windows project is done for the management to save their time. The objective of this project is to help in optimal cost of timely order fulfillment by managing the resources economically with efficient manner

2.2.1 ADVANTAGES

- Time save
- By using online candidates can apply and check the application status
- Proposed System made all the process easy.

3. Module Description

3.1 Admin Authentication

This module is mainly based on admin. System will check the admin user name and password for authentication. After the verification for authorization the admin can be able to precede the process. All works are done under his control.

3.2 Students Information Enrollment

This module fully based on admin control admin can register the students in the registration form admin has to fill with student personal details such as name, address, DOB, class, department and the student mobile number. This module deals with the student academic details and personnel details. This will maintain in a separate table.

3.3 Student Academic info Details

In this module maintain the semester mark information such as student roll no, student name, department year of studying and all semester internal and external maximum marks, the marks obtained for various subjects like its internal, external and total mark. This will maintain in separate table.

3.4 Placement Company information Entry

This module stores all the company details of registered concern. This contains company id, company name, location, available openings, qualification, which will be maintained in the database.

3.5 SMS based alert system

The SMS management is the process of enhancing the SMS service from the application. After successful enter of Company information, the module fetches the important information of the company details such as company name, location, available openings, qualification then send the Interview alert to student mobile number easy and effective manner.

3.6 Report Generation

The admin can generate different reports such as students report, and mark reports. Report generation module is used to generate the reports through crystal report. Report generation module is used to generate and view the details with efficient manner.

4. Scope of Future Development

The application can be extended with several future directions such as SMS notification about their selection, automatic criteria definition and real time practical tests. The application can be hosted and reviewed with real time scenarios. Additional alert and notifications can be performed for effective interview process.

5. Conclusion

It is concluded that the application works well and satisfy both the Admin. The application is tested very well and errors are properly debugged. The proposed system is to provide an easy way maintain placement and filtration details systematic way get the details easily. This system is to provide an easy way to automate all functionalities of a placement hiring process the implementation of this application, which helps the management and company.

The proposed system personalizes the recruitment process in the placement cell with the considerations of marks and test results. The application provides an effective way to shortlist the students to the placement activity based on different criteria. The application initially collects students personal and academic details along with the test score and then performs the criteria match.

6. Bibliography

Books Referred:

- [1] Alex Homer, 'Professional VB.NET 1.1', 2004 Edition, Wrox Publications
- [2] Clayton crooks II 'Learning Visual Basic .Net Through Applications'
- [3] Roger S Pressman, 'Software Engineering', 2000 Edition, Dreamtech Publications
- [4] Steven Holzner, 'Visual Basic.NET Black Book', 2003 Edition, Dreamtech Publications
- [5] A. Keyton Weissinger, "ASP IN A NUTSHELL", Shroff Publishers and distributors Pvt.Ltd, February 1999
- [6] A. Russel Jones, "ASP.NET Complete Reference", Sybex Publications, February 18,2002
- [7] DATABASE SYSTEM CONCEPTS, Henry F.Korth, Megraw-Hill, Third Edition, 1997.
- [8] Steven Holzner, 'C#.NET Black Book', 2003 Edition, Dreamtech Publications
- [9] SQL SERVER HIGH AVAILABILITY, Paul Bertucci, Sams publishing, First Edition, 2004. [5]. SOFTWARE ENGINEERING ONCEPT, Richared E. Fairly Tata Megraw-Hill Publications, Third Edition, 1997.